

RESIDUAL THERMAL STRESS ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF FUNCTIONALLY GRADIENT COATINGS ON CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, residual thermal stress in coatings of carbon-carbon composites for use in nozzle of liquid propulsion rocket engine has been analyzed by a finite element method using a 3D element model. It was assumed that the coating has a controlled compositional gradient and its thickness is varied. The results show that controlling the composition of the interlayer is an effective way to reduce the normal residual thermal stress in coatings and the greatest reduction of residual thermal stresses can be obtained by optimization design of compositional gradient in coatings. To verify the analysis, experiments were also conducted. The computer simulations match the experimental results fairly well.

INTRODUCTION

The development of structural carbon materials in the form of carbon-fiber-reinforced carbon matrix (Carbon-Carbon) composites has received increasing emphasis over the past years. Potential uses has been identified in future generation military aircraft, advanced missile systems, and a variety of hypersonic aerospace vehicles. All of these applications take advantage of the high temperature capabilities of carbon and the benefits of fiber reinforcement. The carbon-carbon composite provides superior specific strength and significantly enhanced temperature capability. Based on their mechanical performance, carbon-carbon composites have been identified as attractive materials for use in applications requiring strength, light weight and toughness where temperature may exceed 2000 °C^[1]. However, these applications involved extended periods of operation in oxidizing environments, a serious drawback is that carbon in any form will react with oxygen, burning away rapidly at temperatures as low as 500 °C^[2]. Great interest is therefore being focussed on the possibility of coating C/C composites with protective layers which will be impermeable to oxygen at 1000 °C and above^[3]. Unfortunately, because of thermal expansion differences and poor wetting properties, most ceramic materials do not form satisfactory coatings on carbon composites. Layers of, for example, silicon carbide applied by chemical vapor desposition to C/C composites rapidly

develop cracks during thermal cycling. Other coatings made by reaction sintering, such as SiC and SiO₂ when applied to C/C composites also give incomplete oxidation protection. It has been shown recently that coatings with controlled compositional gradient are effective in protecting against oxidation in air at high temperature. The present paper analyzes the residual thermal stresses of reaction sintering coatings and discusses the optimum design of functionally gradient coatings on carbon-carbon composites.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL

The carbon/carbon composites sheet materials used in this study were made from viscose or PAN-based carbon cloth and a carbonized phenolic resin matrix. Reinforced plastic molding techniques were used to fabricate the precursor composites (carbon/phenolic) which were subsequently heat treated to convert the phenolic resin matrix to carbon. In this step, the precursor composites are cured and post cured to 290°C, and carbonized in nitrogen atmosphere to 850°C. The next step in the process is densification processing. A schematic of a typical densification process of the type described is shown in Fig. 1. As can be seen, multiple cycles consisting of vacuum impregnation at 170°C, carbonization to over 850°C, must be carried out to reduce the porosity to an acceptable level. The number of densification cycles required to fully process a carbon-carbon composite will vary depending on the impregnant and the process used. In this study, the impregnation-heat treatment cycle is repeated 3~5 times to complete the process. The final composite had a density of 1.32 g/cm³ and 1.48g/cm³. Mechanical properties measured on carbon-carbon composites prepared from these preforms are presented in Table 1. These data show that the use of PAN-based fabric in carbon-carbon composite resulted in high strength, high density, and low thermal expansion and thermal conductivity. PAN-based carbon-carbon composites are the good substrate of oxidation resistant C/C composites.

Fig. 1. Typical carbon-carbon process schematic

Table 1 Mechanical properties of 2D carbon-carbon composites

Property	PAN-based fabric	Viscose filament fabric
Tensile Strength(MPa)	124	19.9
Tensile modulus(GPa)	86.7	14.5
Compressive strength(MPa)	100	57.0
Compressive modulus(GPa)	38.5	22.0
Coef of thermal expansion(10 ⁻⁶ /k)	0.97	2.34
Thermal Conductivity(W/m.k)	1.97	3.73
Composite density (g/cm ³)	1.48	1.32

The oxidation protection method described in this paper was a coating system composed of an inner reaction sintering SiC layer, tetraethylorthosilicate (TEOS) interlayer and a seal coating on the surface. Firstly, the carbon-carbon composite is buried in the slurries of refractory compounds, such as silicon-silicon carbide- Al_2O_3 mixtures, and then heated to 1600°C to fuse the SiC phase, physical incompatibility exists between such SiC coatings and the carbon-carbon substrate because of their different thermal expansion behaviour. Cracks are therefore formed in the coating and the interphase. Additional impregnation with SiO_2 -forming liquids such as tetraethylorthosilicate (TEOS) improves the protection. Better long-term protection against oxidation than with only SiC coatings can be achieved by spraying or dipping in molten silicon oxide. Table 2 gives the effect of carbon-carbon substrates on the weight gain and thickness of coatings. The results suggested that the viscose-based fibre was easy to react with silicon and the thicker coating could be formed in a given time.

Table 2 The weight gain and thickness of coatings on different carbon-carbon substrates

Substrate	temp($^\circ\text{C}$)	time(min)	Weight gain (mg/cm 2)	thickness of coating (min)	Specimen
Viscose-based	1650	60	56.6	0.7	50×50×10mm
PAN-based	1680	90	35.5	0.5	

RESIDUAL THERMAL STRESS ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF COATINGS

The above experimental studies have shown that when defining systems for protecting high performance carbon-carbon, mechanical compatibility becomes an overriding issue and provides substantial insight into the coating-substrate system response. The carbon-carbon composite has a substantially lower thermal expansion coefficient within fiber reinforced lamina than any ceramic exhibiting a symmetric crystal structure. Since deposits are normally made at elevated temperature, microcracked coatings result. This phenomena could be simulated by finite element method using a 3D element model. The maximum residual thermal stress of SiC coatings on two kinds of carbon-carbon composite substrates is 537MPa and 581MPa. It obviously exceeds the tensile strength of reaction bonded SiC coatings. Thus, the single SiC coatings are not effective in protecting C/C composites against oxidation in air at high temperature because of the microcracks on the surface. Generally, the oxidation threshold for carbon-carbon is $\approx 370^\circ\text{C}$. This can be improved to $\approx 600^\circ\text{C}$ by the incorporation of refractory particulate as inhibitors^[4]. The intrinsic protective range of the coating is defined by the microcracking temperature and the coating limiting-use temperature. In this range, the cracks are mechanically closed and sealed by oxidation products. It is clear that technology to seal cracks in the range from $\approx 600^\circ\text{C}$ to the microcracking temperature must be employed for successful full range oxidation protection. For these reasons, two kinds of oxidation-protection systems are presented in the following discussion.

(1) **Multilayer Coatings** A candidate coating system for improving the oxidation protection could be constructed based on the following principles. The SiC ceramics have the best thermal expansion compatibility and exhibit the lowest oxidation rates of the high temperature ceramics. Thus, the reaction bonded SiC coating could serve as an inner layer to interface with the carbon-carbon substrate and provide a carbon diffusion barrier for the oxides. An SiO_2 interlayer for densification is formed by TEOS decomposition. Five cycles consisting of vacuum impregnation of TEOS and thermal de-

composition at 100°C, and the final cure and decomposition at 315°C are employed to fill the microcracks on the SiC coated C/C specimens. In the last step, an SiO₂ mixtures could be used as the sealant for cracks in the outer coating. The three-layer coating then consists of silicon carbide/TEOS/SiO₂ mixture sealant. Table 3 compares the oxidation resistance of different coated C/C composites. These data show that multiple-layer coated C/C composites have the required thermal stability for use at 1300°C.

Table 3 Oxidation behaviour of C/C specimen coated with different layers

Substrate	Experimental	Weight loss (g/m ² · S)		
		SiC layer	SiC+TEOS	SiC+TEOS+SiO ₂
Viscose-based	1300°C, 1h	-0.0857	-0.0088	—
PAN-based	1300°C, 1h	-0.0707	—	-0.0076

(2) **Functionally Gradient Coatings** In order to reduce the residual thermal stress, the interlayer with controlled compositional gradient from carbon to silicon carbide is suggested to eliminate the thermal expansion mismatch. The influence of the compositional gradient and thickness of the interlayer on the residual thermal stress is analyzed by finite element method. It is demonstrated in Fig. 2 that the functionally gradient coatings result the obvious decrease of residual thermal stress. The decreasing maximum residual thermal stress of SiC coating with its increased thickness is shown in Fig. 3. Let the compositional gradient is as follows:

$$V_B = \frac{V_B}{V_A + V_B} = f(\xi) = \begin{cases} f_0 & 0 \leq \xi \leq \xi_0 \\ (f_1 - f_0) \left[\frac{\xi - \xi_0}{\xi_1 - \xi_0} \right]^n & \xi_0 \leq \xi \leq \xi_1 \\ f_1 & \xi_1 \leq \xi \leq 1 \end{cases}$$

where, V_A and V_B are the volume fraction of SiC and carbon in the gradient interlayer, respectively; ξ₀, ξ and ξ₁ are the thickness of C/C, interlayer and SiC coating; f₀, f, f₁ are the volume fraction of SiC in the substrate, interlayer and outer coating, n is the power parameter of compositional gradient. Fig 4 shows the variation of the maximum thermal stress with power parameter of compositional gradient. All the results show that controlling the compositional gradient and thickness of the interlayer is an effective way to reduce the normal residual thermal stress in coatings and the greatest reduction can be obtained by optimization design of compositional gradient in coatings.

CONCLUSION

Long term oxidation protection of carbon-carbon composites at high temperature is a very challenging problem. The current state of the art in protective coating is based on the use of the silicon carbide coatings. Experimental and finite element analysis demonstrate that only the single SiC coating is not an effective barrier to inward diffusion of oxygen because of microcracks induced by thermal expansion mismatch. In this paper, the SiC/TEOS/SiO₂ multiple layers and functionally gradient coatings have proved to be the most important coating systems. Such a multilayer coating based on SiC coupled with internal inhibitors of TEOS and SiO₂ sealants to seal thermal stress cracks and defects in SiC coatings, possesses the necessary chemical stability. By the optimization of functionally gradient coatings, the maximum thermal stress in SiC

Fig. 2 The maximum σ_y as a function of distance of surface

Fig. 3 The effect of thickness of SiC layer on the maximum σ_y

Fig. 4 The effect of power of compositional gradient on the maximum σ_y

coating could be reduced to about 40%.

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